

Archiving and Databases (DHL5040)

Trimester III, AY2020-2021

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Write an essay on the preservation of cultural heritage using digital technologies. You may use examples to illustrate your argument.

The information era has steadily transformed our lifestyles, society, and cultures, providing enormous resources and also exceptional challenges. The modern world dwells in daily cultural rituals. It enhanced our way of thought, determining, and realizing our objective. So the digital environment becomes an integral part of human life.

“Digital Information lasts forever

- or five years, whichever comes first”

- Jeff Rothenberg

Humanities are an integral part of any culture and heritage institution. To collect organize and maintain humanities and social science document is a big challenge in any institution. Liberal arts and Humanities use the word ‘culture’ to refer to a way of life. Every human society has a culture (Ekwelem, 2011). Culture encompasses the society’s arts, faiths, traditions, structures, developments, language, innovation and principles. Several people in a community can develop similar habits and thoughts as a result of culture. As a result, cultural legacy preserves people's way of life, practices, and rituals from generation to generation. The cultural heritage assets are priceless artefacts with a very important historical and moral value (Belhi, 2017). It might be the only instrument capable of tracing a humanity's lifespan and hence transferring information and knowledge over centuries. Conserving these assets is a top priority for all nations (Belhi, 2017). Cultural heritage can contribute towards well-being and quality of life of communities, can help to mitigate the impacts of cultural globalization (Gražulevičiūtė, 2006).

To preserve our past memory, cultural habits, we may use different digital technologies. In this respect Digital preservation is a new approach with a modern way of thinking, provides

archivists, librarians, and other cultural history professionals for memory institutions (Library, Archive, Museum, Art Gallery etc.).

Digital preservation is a collection of management practices that supports sustainable access to online resources for as long as needed. Digital records are particularly vulnerable to technical problems such as equipment/ software obsolescence, as well as bit rot, however, IT approaches such as trustable electronic backup and recovery are play a role in the overall picture. Preservation covers a broad variety of institutional asset problems, such as risk evaluation, conservation, strategy, capability creation, and regulatory compliance.

Edward. M. Corrado, told that (Corrado, 2017) “traditional information source such as books, photos and sculptures can easily survive for years and decades or even centuries but digital items are fragile and require special care to keep them usable”. Because of the rapid growth of technological transformation, digital files may become impossible to access after they were produced. According to Edward. M. Corrado digital preservation has five basic elements “Provenance” “Reference information” “Fixity” “Context” “Access Right”. When developing a digital preservation system for a cultural heritage organization, we must understand the originality of a document, which is referred to as provenance. Since digital documents can be replicated at any time, so it’s very difficult to identify the original author of a specific document/ text when it is converted from tangible to intangible digital property. Fixity refers to the distinction between being a born-digital and digital surrogate. Digital preservation is not possible without content. We need to update our content regularly. Another critical area is digital accessibility; organizations must provide access to material records, including storage, dissemination, and use.

If we consider Digital archives space, they change their meaning over time and are continually replicating versions of physical records in the digital space. Virtual space isn't neutral. It is infested with class relations, politics and inequalities. The virtual space has a distinct perception, experiences and memories, that depending on the programming language.. Whereas tangible spaces are collectively built, created, mediated, and developed, negotiated, virtual spaces are more customisable and easy to control, despite the fact that we can forcibly model these spaces, such as Google Classroom. Since digital archives are versatile and temporary, they transform more easily than conventional archives. It has benefits and drawbacks; computerised records can vanish almost immediately, but it can also be quickly safeguarded and recovered.

One general misunderstanding is that making carbon copy versions of files is equivalent to digital preservation, but it's not like that. A well-established emergency preparedness system is an essential component of digital reconstruction, and simply supplying backups is inadequate to "ensure ongoing access" (Corrado, 2017). The digital back up file is generated by the compilation of bit streams preservation. Backup is mostly done with proprietary software that helps users to access files that have been backed up at different times (Kirchhoff, 2008). The backup of records is not a safeguard against technological advancements.

Simply establishing a digital warehouse or institutional repository would not constitute an engagement in digital preservation. For example, a digital archive allows access to inherent resources but does not necessarily have the consistent maintenance that is required for long term continuous access. One of the major goal of digital preservation is to provide the digital content on paly. So that it allows any person to read, interpret, download, archive, share, print, search, or connect to the full text (Corrado, 2017). If we consider the National Archives of India, they converts most of the physical objects to digital format but only makes it available to those who visit their campus. It is not freely accessible on the internet, so digital preservation raises the question of what the utility and accessibility of the digital material are.

The technology can be applied at all stages of cultural heritage management, including digitization, restoration, display, and conservation (Belhi, 2017). Digital platforms have created a set of possibilities to address concerns related to cultural exchange and information access (Belhi A. e., 2019). Nowadays 3D technology is used to create 3D modelling of heritage institution for digital embodiment of a particular objects. For an example Digital Hampi project by IIT Delhi where they created 3D avatars of Temples and people. So that people can easily envision and visualize these historic sites and their cultures. In the preservation method, an AI-based machine learning approach and an IoT model are used to predict data. Assume we are detecting an old heritage architecture of a building and do not know the older iteration of the building, in which case this sort of model is really useful.

One major reason for digital record obsolescence is technological obsolescence. Rapid technological developments would not fix the major issue however, we must change digital content from one technical format to another. (Chadha, 2009). Devices for interpreting these materials quickly become outdated, as well as the different platforms for multimedia records and images, bring more complexities. The concept of digital preservation is focused on the

conservation and upkeep of the digital framework in which material is created, such as OS, hardware and software, media device, etc. which is known as “computer museum”

When we searched for anything on the internet, we found the most important facts based on our search words. We don't know whether the source content is authentic or not. For that purpose, cultural heritage institutions are used OAIS RM (Open Archival Information System Reference Model) model to create trustworthy material. There are two types of trust that are produced by OAIS reference model. The first is created when a consumer deposits authentic content to a specific organization. The second is generated by the organization to offer to its end users. One good example may be the Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts' Digital Preservation Scheme. They developed various information systems as well as a database of arts and humanities materials. They have authentic multimedia content. They cover a wide range of topics including archaeology, theology, faith and ceremonial studies, history and anthropology, art and literature, and folk, cultural, and community studies.

Materiality is described as the appearance of items, materials, or others in one's physical environment whereas immateriality attracts implications due to its perishability and lack of form and function. (Ibrahim, 2018). Digital documents can be replicated at any point of time. When a physical object change to digital format, it changes its materiality. The tangible property change to the form of intangible. The power of an archive comes to its physicality, but when it converted to digital material the power also changes.

To protect Digital documents, maintaining IPR, Copyright, CC license is a big challenge in any heritage institution Each organisation should consider if the content it attempts to protect is in the public domain or whether the copyright is held by someone other than the organisation. This might wish to seek out the copyright holder to license the rights required to protect writing.

Migration is a wider data management phenomenon. Migration is a set of organized tasks designed to achieve the periodic transfer of digital materials from one hardware / software configuration to another, or from one generation of computer technology to a subsequent generation (Chadha, 2009). Similarly, emulation incorporates software and hardware to replicate the output of some other device of a distinct magnitude in all important features enabling programmes or media programmed for a specific context to run.

Moreover digital technology provide huge opportunities for cultural heritage institution to collect, organize, maintain their content in a broad spectrum. Various digital tools have an

impact on the quality of the institution's performance and reduce issues with service efficiency created by human actors.

The intangible processes of the online web will weaken the smoothness and immateriality of the digital realm, as well as its potential to reshape human projects of restoration by recalling and remembering. Derrida alludes to in virtuality are not just about the unlimited knowledge they can potentially hold but the potential to thwart the morality while transacting memory through a sphere which is ineradicable (Ibrahim, 2018).

Reference:

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